

Studies on physicochemical parameters in relation with fish ecology in Futiyari Reservoir, Purulia, West Bengal, India.

Manab Kumar Saha

Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, Ramananda Centenary College, Laulara, Purulia-723151, West Bengal, India.

Abstract:

A study was carried out from March 2017 to December 2018 to investigate the ichthyofaunal diversity, abundance, and conservation status in relation to the water quality of the rain-fed reservoir 'Futiyari Reservoir' of Purulia District, West Bengal, India. The study revealed the occurrence of 39 fish species is included in 6 orders and 14 families. Observation shows that the Cypriniformes were the dominant order followed by Perciformes, Siluriformes, Osteoglossiformes, Anguilliformes, and Beloniformes. Physicochemical parameters of water such as temperature, Dissolved Oxygen, pH, Transparency, Conductivity, alkalinity, Chloride, Phosphate, Total inorganic nitrogen, hardness, Salinity, Photic depth, free CO₂ were recorded. These factors also influence the optimum growth of natural plankton which is the primary source of food for the fish community. Taken as a whole, the physico-chemical parameters indicate the safe mean value of standard aquatic quality, which were tolerable for aquaculture for the period of the survey. But, measures should be taken to maintain the sustainability of the ichthyofaunal diversity in the rain-fed reservoir.

Key words: Ichthyofaunal Diversity, Physicochemical Parameter, Hydro-Ecology, Rain Fed reservoir.

Introduction:

Purulia is the westernmost district of West Bengal and geographically it is the lowest part of 'Chhota Nagpur Plateau' of eastern India. Several small and medium water reservoirs are present in this district (Roy, 2013, Bera et al 2014). In general, the reservoir means a large natural or artificial space for freshwater storage. Freshwater is the only resource used for drinking and irrigation purposes (Chowdhury et al., 2017; Costanza et al., 2017; Hu et al., 2018). The Futiyari Reservoir not only fulfils the two major purposes but also has economic, medicinal, cultural, social, aesthetic value, and used as the livelihood in the form of aquaculture and fisheries (Gupta et al., 2012; Pradhan et al., 2015; Mandalet al., 2020). The people of West Bengal are highly dependent upon daily fish meals. Subsequently, it creates pressure on freshwater bodies; Futiyari Reservoir is not an exception (Verma et al., 2018). Fishes are widely considered as 'ecological indicators' to examine the ecological status of any aquatic ecosystem (Sarma et al., 2010; Vijaylaxmi et al., 2010, Sonawane et al., 2015). There are very few works that have been done on Ichthyofaunal diversity in the Purulia district (Roy et al., 2013; Mondal et al., 2015; Pradhan et al., 2015). Still, there is some lack of information on the Ichthyofauna diversity concerning water quality. So, to fill this lacuna, an

initiative has been made to investigate the relationship between ichthyofaunal diversity and various physico-chemical parameters and the hydro-ecology of water for the ‘Futiaryi’ reservoir to make a sustainable conservation plan.

Material and Methods:

Study Area:

Fig. 1. Location map of the study area. Satellite image of Futiaryi Reservoir at Purulia district, West Bengal, India.

The rain-fed ‘Futiaryi Reservoir’ is located near Kalabani Gram Panchayet, Hura block of Purulia district in West Bengal, India and lies on 86.5577°E and 23.3833°N coordinates. The total water spread area of the reservoir is 303 ha. The shortest distance from Purulia station is about 23 km. Construction of this Dam was to look after the economically underdeveloped areas of the district by reducing the water scarcity.

Sampling:

During the survey period from March 2017 to December 2018 sampling was done bi-monthly (every second and fourth week of each month), early in the morning (within 8:30 am). The water temperature was recorded by a portable digital thermometer (LCD ST-9283B) and the air temperature was recorded by Digital Hygro Thermometer (HTC Instrument 288-ATH); pH recorded by digital pH meter (Cystronics model 335); Dissolved Oxygen examined by portable D.O. meter (Hi-tech Lab India); conductivity analyzed by a digital conductivity meter (Labtronics LT-16); Photic Depth measured by black & white Secchi disc method. Free CO₂, Chlorinity,

Alkalinity, Total Inorganic Nitrogen, Calcium, Magnesium, and Hardness, Phosphorus were calculated as standard laboratory protocols (APHA, 2017).

The fish samples were captured from five fixed sampling sites from the reservoir. The local skilled fishermen were helping a lot in fish collection with different fishing gears viz. drag net, cast net, scoop net, gill net, including hooks and lines, etc. Only a few 'indicative specimens' from captured fishes were preserved in 8% formalin solution for further identification (Jayaram, 1981; Talwar 1991; Jhingran 1975), and the rest fish samples were photographed immediately before release them into the reservoir at the same place. Local villagers employed net (Phasi jal) in the evening and collect the catch early in the morning throughout the year, but winter (Dec-Feb) is the peak fishing season. Zooplankton was collected with the help of plankton net. The entire sample was centrifuged, decanted, and concentrated to make 1 ml volume for observation under S-R (Sedgwick-Rafter) counting cell. Four major groups viz. Cladocera, Copepoda, Ostracoda, and Rotifera were identified among the zooplankton population. The bimonthly average data for each season were added together to get the average annual value which reflects the overall hydro-ecological scenario of the reservoir (Table 3). The Fish diversity index, regression analysis (Pearsons correlation r) was carried out to verify the affinities among the physicochemical parameters by using Stat Plus software (Hammer, 2001) and Microsoft Excel (2007) software. All the parameters were compared with water quality standards (Boyd and Tucker, 1998; Ali *et al.*, 2000) in relation to their suitability to sustain aquatic species in the selected sites. The present conservation status of fishes in the Futiyari Reservoir was compared with IUCN conservation status (IUCN-Version 2020.1).

Results and Discussion:

The data regarding the fish community of the Futiyari Reservoir (reservoir) are shown in Tables 2 and the water parameters are illustrated in Table 3. The periodic report of the ichthyofauna diversity showed that the presence of 39 species belonging to 6 orders and 14 families. On the basis of species composition, Cypriniformes were dominant (19 species) followed by Perciformes (each of 10 species) and Siluriformes (6 species), Osteoglossiformes (2 species), Anguilliformes and Beloniformes (each of 1 species). Majority of the fishes of the rain feed reservoir are the least concern (LC) category, in keeping with IUCN status. Among the reported fishes six species are nearly threatened (NT), three species are not evaluated (NE) and one species is falling under the Critically Endangered (CR) categories. It was noted that *Catla catla*, *Labeo rohita* and *Oreochromis mossambicus* were very common fish for the fishermen and villagers during the study period. Apart from that *Puntius sophore*, *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Salmophasia bacaila*, *Chanda nama* and *Channa punctata* were repeatedly harvested small fishes from the study area.

It has been well established that the abiotic factors (Physico-chemical parameters) have a great influence on the fish development, growth, immunization and, Reproductive maturity. According to the scientist (Bhatnagar et al., 2013), the vital factors are- temperature, Dissolved Oxygen, pH, Transparency, Conductivity, Alkalinity, Chloride, Phosphate, Total inorganic nitrogen, hardness,

Salinity, Photic depth and, free CO₂, etc. As per recommendation of FAO (2012) report, temperature is a curtail factor for aquaculture and fish culture.

The study area showed an average temperature range between 25-30°C which is appropriate for freshwater fish culture. Among the abiotic factors temperature is one of the most vital factors for the aquaculture. As per the FAO (2012) guideline, the fish growth, distribution and production has a direct and indirect relationship with water temperature. It is reported that the appropriate water temperature in the tropical region for carp culture is ranging from 24°C and 30°C. The average water temperature of Futiyari reservoir was very suitable for fish culture, though a little fall during the winter season was recorded. Experimentally it is established that the pH is another important parameter for fish culture. pH shows a restrictive controlling over fish growth and survival. The best result shows ranging between 6 and 9 (Boyd and Tucker, 1998; Ali et al., 2000). The pH value observed in the reservoir was within the optimum range. Transparency helps to assess the quality of water. According to Ali et al., (2000) transparency of a pond between 30-60cm indicates most favourable range for fish culture. Light transparency is proportionally related and ensures the phytoplankton growth. Water transparency in the Futiyari reservoir was partially satisfactory. Electrical conductivity is an important chemical indicator, which indicates the total dissolved ions and is a crucial as nutrients for aquatic life. According to the report of Boyd and Tucker (1998) the suitable range of conductivity is 20-1500 $\mu\text{mho cm}^{-1}$ for fish culture. The study showed lower values in the study area. Alkalinity is the capability of water to counterbalance acidification. It is dependent relative on the existence of certain chemicals in the water like carbonates, bicarbonates, hydroxides, etc. According to the guidelines of Boyd and Tucker, (1998) the ideal value of alkalinity for fish culture is 50–150mg L⁻¹. So, the alkalinity range of Futiyari reservoir permits the Fisheries activity.

Table 1. ‘Diversity index of fish assemblages among the five different sampling station of Futiyari Reservoir, Purulia district during the study period’.

Site	Species Richness (D)	Shannon-wiener index (H')	Evenness index (J)	Simpson's dominance index (D)	Simpson's diversity index (1-D)
I	1.58	3.20	0.51	0.05	0.95
II	1.57	3.19	0.51	0.05	0.95
III	1.58	3.19	0.51	0.05	0.95
IV	1.64	3.18	0.51	0.05	0.95
V	1.69	3.12	0.50	0.05	0.95
Total	0.72	3.19	0.51	0.05	0.95

According to Boyd and Tucker (1998), more than 100mg L⁻¹ is harmful for fisheries activity but chlorides are harmless at low levels. Phosphorus is a curtail element responsible for maintaining sustainable aquaculture. During the study period, value of phosphate in Futiyari Reservoir matched

Table 2: Fish species available in Futiyari reservoir during the study period.

Order	Family	Scientific name	Local name	IUCN	Population	Feeding habit		
Anguilliformes	Anguillidae	1. <i>Anguilla bengalensis</i> (Gray, 1831)	Ban fish	NT	ST	OMV		
Beloniformes	Belonidae	2. <i>Xenentodon cancila</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Kakia	LC	DE	OMV		
Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	3. <i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Mourola	LC	ST	HEV		
		4. <i>Amblypharyngodon microlepis</i> (Bleeker, 1853)	Mourala	LC	ST	HEV		
		5. <i>Catla catla</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Catla	LC	ST	HEV		
		6. <i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Mrigal	LC	UN	OMV		
		7. <i>Cirrhinus reba</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Bhangon bata	LC	DE	OMV		
		8. <i>Cyprinus carpio</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Cyprinus	CR	ST	OMV		
		9. <i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	Silver carp	NT	DE	HEV		
		10. <i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	Grass carp	NE	ST	HEV		
		11. <i>Esomus danricus</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Darkina	LC	DE	HEV		
		12. <i>Labeo calbasu</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Kalbose	LC	ST	HEV		
		13. <i>Labeo bata</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Bata	LC	ST	HEV		
		14. <i>Labeo rohita</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Rui	LC	ST	HEV		
		15. <i>Osteobrama cotio cotio</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Keti	LC	DE	HEV		
		16. <i>Puntius ticto</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Punti	LC	DE	HEV		
		17. <i>Puntius sophore</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Punti	LC	ST	HEV		
		18. <i>Puntius gelius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Dor punti	LC	ST	HEV		
		19. <i>Puntius conchoni</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Punti	VU	DE	HEV		
		20. <i>Rasbora daniconius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Siram punti	LC	DE	ONV		
		21. <i>Salmophasia bacaila</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Chel	LC	UN	OMV		
		Osteoglossiformes	Notopteridae	22. <i>Notopterus chitala</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Chital	NT	ST	OMV
				23. <i>Channa orientalis</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	Cheng	NE	DE	OMV
Perciformes	Ambassidae	24. <i>Chanda ranga</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Ranjan chanda	NE	ST	OMV		
		25. <i>Chanda nama</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Kanta chanda	LC	ST	OMV		
	Anabantidae	26. <i>Anabas testudineus</i> (Bloch, 1792)	Koi	DD	DE	OMV		
		Cichlidae	27. <i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Nilontica	LC	UN	OMV	
	28. <i>Oreochromis mossambicus</i> (Peters, 1852)		Tilapia	NT	ST	OMV		
	Channidae	29. <i>Channa punctata</i> (Bloch, 1793)	Lata	LC	UN	CAV		
		30. <i>Channa striata</i> (Bloch, 1793)	Shol	LC	DE	CAV		
	Gobiidae	31. <i>Glossogobius giuris</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Bele	LC	DE	CAV		
	Osphronemidae	32. <i>Trichogaster fasciata</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)	Kholisha	LC	DE	OMV		
33. <i>Trichogaster lalius</i> (Hamilton, 1822)		Khoira	LC	DE	OMV			
Siluriformes	Bagridae	34. <i>Mystus tengara</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Tangra	LC	ST	CAV		
		35. <i>Mystus vittatus</i> (Bloch, 1794)	Tangra	LC	ST	CAV		
	Claridae	36. <i>Clarias batrachus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Magur	LC	DE	CAV		
	Heteropneustidae	37. <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> (Bloch, 1794)	Singhi	LC	DE	CAV		
	Siluridae	38. <i>Ompok pabda</i> (Hamilton, 1822)	Pabda	NT	DE	CAV		
39. <i>Wallago attu</i> (Bloch & Schneider, 1801)		Boal	NT	ST	CAV			

(IUCN Red list- **DD**: Data Deficient, **LC**: Least Concern, **VU**: Vulnerable, **NE**: Not Evaluated, **EN**: Endangered, **NT**: Near Threatened; Population Trend- **DE**: Decreasing, **UN**: Unknown, **ST**: Stable; **HEV**: Herbivore, **OMV**: Omnivore, **CAV**: Carnivore).

Table 3. ‘Mean values (Mean \pm SE) of physicochemical parameters of water in the Futiyari Reservoir, Purulia district from March 2017 to December 2018.

Parameters			Pre-Monsoon (Mar–May)	Monsoon (June–Sept)	Post-Monsoon (Oct–Nov)	Winter (Dec–Feb)	STRD
1.	Air Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	AT	35.615 \pm 2.84	32.55 \pm 1.85	27.03 \pm 2.25	22.35 \pm 2.28	NA
2.	Water Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	WT	29.24 \pm 2.78	28.65 \pm 2.44	22.67 \pm 2.84	15.41 \pm 3.04	20-32
3.	Dissolved Oxygen (mg L $^{-1}$)	DO	8.02 \pm 1.05	10.8 \pm 1.24	8.6 \pm 1.02	10.21 \pm 1.02	> 1 \geq 5
4.	p ^H	PH	6.09 \pm 0.14	6.02 \pm 0.07	6.05 \pm 0.7	7.02 \pm 0.06	6.5-9
5.	Transparency (cm)	TRA	51.74 \pm 10.44	62.04 \pm 8.09	74.51 \pm 9.02	76.71 \pm 10.05	> 30-60
6.	Conductivity (μ S cm $^{-1}$)	CON	28.21 \pm 3.21	25.14 \pm 2.64	22.56 \pm 3.24	21.58 \pm 2.24	20-1500
7.	Alkalinity (mg L $^{-1}$)	AL	68.64 \pm 8.25	56.84 \pm 5.12	52.96 \pm 4.29	76.64 \pm 9.24	50-150
8.	Chloride (mg L $^{-1}$)	CHC	26.96 \pm 4.09	21.64 \pm 2.88	12.65 \pm 2.89	8.86 \pm 2.21	1-100
9.	Phosphate (mg L $^{-1}$)	PHE	0.012 \pm 0.021	0.075 \pm 0.015	0.092 \pm 0.017	0.034 \pm 0.016	0.005- 0.05
10.	Total inorganic nitrogen (mg L $^{-1}$)	TIN	0.49 \pm 0.09	0.28 \pm 0.07	0.86 \pm 0.06	0.46 \pm 0.04	0.12-2.2
11.	Hardness (ppm)	HAR	125.89 \pm 14.21	139.89 \pm 11.44	142.36 \pm 10.37	114.26 \pm 10.81	>20 ; 50-150
12.	Salinity (ppt)	SAL	0.38 \pm 0.04	0.31 \pm 0.05	0.28 \pm 0.07	0.24 \pm 0.06	\leq 0.5
13.	Photic depth (cm)	PD	54.26 \pm 12.21	89.35 \pm 11.26	92.41 \pm 9.48	57.26 \pm 8.29	66-80
14.	Free CO ₂ (ppm)	FC	3.21 \pm 0.56	3.51 \pm 1.02	3.96 \pm 1.51	4.12 \pm 1.62	>10
15.	Zooplankton density (ind L $^{-1}$)	ZD	1583 \pm 59.36	1195 \pm 46.32	1079 \pm 39.84	1425 \pm 48.61	NA
16.	Average Fish Density (Individual)	AFD	1568	2112	1964	1698	NA

Legend: SE: Standard Error; **STRD**: Standards of water quality (Boyd and Tucker, 1998; Ali et al., 2000).

Table 4. Pearson's r correlation matrix between abiotic and biotic parameters at Futiyari Reservoir, Purulia district during the study period.

Correlation Coefficients (Pairwise deletion)																
	AT	WT	DO	PH	TRA	CON	AL	CHC	PHE	TIN	HAR	SAL	PD	FC	ZD	FSR
AT	1.0000															
WT	0.9848	1.0000														
DO	-0.9778	-0.9990	1.0000													
PH	-0.7998	-0.8703	0.8704	1.0000												
TRA	-0.9498	-0.8881	0.8766	0.5736	1.0000											
CON	0.9535	0.8881	-0.8733	-0.5984	-0.9959	1.0000										
AL	-0.3222	-0.4637	0.4779	0.8164	0.0101	-0.0308	1.0000									
CHC	0.9837	0.9461	-0.9383	-0.6794	-0.9889	0.9846	-0.1537	1.0000								
PHE	-0.1985	-0.0330	0.0081	-0.3932	0.4882	-0.4837	-0.8505	-0.3535	1.0000							
TIN	-0.2780	-0.2642	0.2879	-0.1546	0.4270	-0.3454	-0.3694	-0.3992	0.3859	1.0000						
HAR	0.4032	0.5412	-0.5556	-0.8584	-0.0975	0.1148	-0.9956	0.2406	0.8091	0.3025	1.0000					
SAL	0.9574	0.8958	-0.8769	-0.6728	-0.9678	0.9860	-0.1224	0.9649	-0.4151	-0.1860	0.1988	1.0000				
PD	-0.8559	-0.7549	0.7287	0.4792	0.9358	-0.9586	-0.1096	-0.8960	0.6161	0.1710	0.0382	-0.9670	1.0000			
FC	-0.9762	-0.9313	0.9223	0.6506	0.9945	-0.9904	0.1124	-0.9990	0.3938	0.4062	-0.1996	-0.9686	0.9105	1.0000		
ZD	0.2446	0.0805	0.0556	0.3515	-0.5292	0.5244	0.8267	0.3976	-0.9989	-0.3999	-0.7816	0.4559	-0.6495	-0.4371	1.0000	
FSR	-0.0144	0.1561	-0.1952	-0.3847	0.2509	-0.2890	-0.7395	-0.1184	0.8647	-0.1273	0.7344	-0.2991	0.5294	0.1587	-0.8536	1.0000

Correlations in bold are significant at the 5% level (2-tailed).

the ranges recommend by Boyd and Tucker (1998) i.e. 0.06 mg L⁻¹ for fish culture and surface water is 0.005–0.5 mg L⁻¹. According to Bhatnagar and Devi (2013), both zooplankton and the phytoplankton collectively serve as key food source for fish and fisheries health. The water quality parameters in the reservoir remain within the limit which leads to a high ichthyofaunal diversity, as per different diversity index (table 1) and fish cultivation.

Table 5. Composition of the fish community by family

Sl. No	Family	No. of Species	Percentage (%)
1.	Anguillidae	01	2.56
2.	Belonidae	01	2.56
3.	Cyprinidae	19	48.72
4.	Notopteridae	02	5.13
5.	Ambassidae	02	5.13
6.	Anabantidae	01	2.56
7.	Cichlidae	02	5.13
8.	Channidae	02	5.13
9.	Gobiidae	01	2.56
10.	Osphronemidae	02	5.13
11.	Bagridae	02	5.13
12.	Claridae	01	2.56
13.	Heteropneustidae	01	2.56
14.	Siluridae	02	5.13
Total		39	100

Table 6. Qualitative analysis of zooplanktons present in five different sampling sites of 'Futiyari Reservoir' during study period.

Group	Family	Scientific Name
Cladocera	Daphniidae	1. <i>Ceriodaphnia cornuta</i> (Sars, 1886)
		2. <i>Daphnia carinata</i> (King, 1852)
	Moinidae	3. <i>Moina affinis</i> (Birge, 1893)
		4. <i>Moina brachiata</i> (Jurine, 1820)
	Sididae	5. <i>Sida crystallina</i> (Müller, 1776)
Copepoda	Cyclopidae	6. <i>Cyclops sp.</i> (Müller, 1785)
		7. <i>Mesocyclops leuckarti</i> (Claus, 1857)
Ostracoda	Candonidae	8. <i>Candona candida</i> (Müller, 1776)
	Cyprididae	9. <i>Cypria ophthalmica</i> (Jurine, 1820)
		10. <i>Cyclocypris ovum</i> (Jurine, 1820)
Rotifera	Asplanchnidae	11. <i>Asplanchna brightwelli</i> (Gosse, 1851)
		12. <i>Pompholyx sp.</i> (Gosse, 1851)
	Brachionidae	13. <i>Brachionus plicatillis</i> (Müller, 1786)
		14. <i>Brachionus angularis</i> (Gosse, 1851)
		15. <i>Brachionus quadridentatus</i> (Hermann, 1783)
		16. <i>Brachionus caudatus</i> (Barrois&Dadai, 1894)
		17. <i>Brachionus calyciflorus</i> (Pallas, 1766)
		18. <i>Keratella cochlearis</i> (Gosse, 1851)
		19. <i>Keratella tropica</i> (Apstein, 1907)
Filinidae	20. <i>Filinia longiseta</i> (Ehrenberg, 1834)	

References:

1. Ali M, Salam A, Azeem A, Shafique M, Khan BA. Studies on the effect of seasonal variations on physical and chemical characteristics of mixed water from Rivers Ravi and Chenab at union site in Pakistan. J. Res. BZ Univ.Multan. 2000; 2:1-7.

2. APHA, Standard Methods for Examination of Water and Waste Water, American Public Health Association, Washington, DC, USA, 23rd edition, 2017.
3. Bera A, Bhattacharya M, Patra BC, Sar UK. Ichthyofaunal diversity and water quality in the Kangsabati Reservoir, West Bengal, India. *Advances in Zoology*. 2014; 3(12):28-32.
4. Bhatnagar, A. and Devi, P. (2013). "Water quality guidelines for the management of pond fish culture," *International Journal of Environmental Sciences*, vol. 3(6): 1980–2009.
5. Boyd, C. E., Tucker, C. S. (1998) "Ecology of aquaculture ponds." *Pond aquaculture water quality management*. Springer, Boston, MA., 8-86.
6. Chowdhury, R. R., Uchida, E., Chen, L., Osorio, V., & Yoder, L. (2017). Anthropogenic Drivers of Mangrove Loss: Geographic Patterns and Implications for Livelihoods. In *Mangrove Ecosystems: A Global Biogeographic Perspective*. 275-300. Colwell, R. K. (2009) *Biodiversity: Concepts, Patterns, and Measurement*, Springer, Cham. 257-263. (Copyright Document).
7. Costanza, R., de Groot, R., Braat, L., Kubiszewski, I., Fioramonti, L., Sutton, P. and Grasso, M. (2017). Twenty years of ecosystem services: How far have we come and how far do we still need to go? *Ecosystem Services* 28: 1-16.
8. Fisheries, F. A. O. (2012). Aquaculture Department. *The state of world fisheries and aquaculture*, 1-153.
9. Gupta, R. C., Kaushik, T. K. and Gupta, P. K. (2012). Winter migratory wetland birds in Haryana are confronting adverse conditions in rural ponds resulting in reduction in arrival number: A case study of village Amin in Thanesar block in Kurukshetra District. *Indian Journal of Fundamental and Applied Life Sciences* 2(1): 1-7.
10. Hammer, Ø., Harper, D. A., Ryan, P.D., PAST: Paleontological statistics software package for education and data analysis. *Palaeontologia electronica*. 2001; 4(1):9.
11. Hu, T., Pang, C. and Zhou, X. (2018). Say No to the Thirsty Planet: Too Few Freshwater for the Daily Life of Human Beings. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 170(2):022116.
12. IUCN, (2020). "IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (version 2020.1). [Online]. Available at: <http://www.iucnredlist.org/>
13. Jayaram, K. C. *The Freshwater Fishes of India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Burma, and Sri Lanka: Handbook*, Calcutta, India, ZSI, 1981.
14. Jhingran, V. G. *Fish and fisheries of India*, Hindustan Publishing Corporation, New Delhi, India, 1975.
15. Mondal, K., & Patra, A. (2015). Ichthyofaunal diversity of Purulia district, WB, India. *Journal of Global Biosciences*, 4(6), 2590-2593.
16. Nag, S. K., Nandy, S.K., Roy, K., Sarkar, U.K. and Das, B.K. (2019). Carbon balance of a sewage-fed aquaculture wetland. *Wetlands Ecology and Management* 27(2-3): 311-322.

17. Mandal, A., Kaushik, N., Yadav, S.S., Rao, A.S., Singh, N. and Gulia, S.S. (2020). Water Quality Assessment of Pond Water of Kalanaur Block, Rohtak, Haryana. *Indian Journal of Ecology*, 47(1): 1-6.
18. Pradhan, A., Kundu, R. and Bandyopadhyay, N. (2015). Ichthyofaunal diversity of different Reservoirs of Purulia District, West Bengal, India *Journal of Research in Biology*, 5(7): 1850-1859.
19. Roy, C., Vass, K. K., Patra, B. C. and Sanyal, A. K. (2013). Fish diversity in two south-western districts of West Bengal-Bankura and Purulia. *Records of the Zoological Survey of India*, 113(4), 167-179.
20. Sarma, S. K. and Saikia, M. (2010). Utilization of wetland resources by the rural people of Nagaon district, Assam. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge* 9(1): 145-151.
21. Sonawane, D. L. and Barve, M. B. (2015). Ichthyofaunal study of Kasura dam district Jalna (MS) India. *The ecoscan: Special*, (2015), 319-323.
22. Talwar, P. K. and Jhingran, A. G. *Inland Fishes of India and Adjacent Countries*, vol. 1 and 2, Oxford and IBHPub. Co. Pvt.Ltd., New Delhi, India, 1991.
23. Verma, H. O., Gopal, K., Tripathi, S. And Singh, A. (2018). A study on ichthyofaunal diversity and water quality of Bakhira Lake, Uttar Pradesh, India.
24. Vijaylaxmi, C., Rajshekhar, M. And Vijaykumar, K. (2010). Freshwater fishes distribution and diversity status of Mullameri River, a minor tributary of Bheema River of Gulbarga District, Kamataka. *International Journal of Systems Biology*, 2(2), 1.